

Arctic haze in a climate changing world: the 2010–2022 trend (HAZECLIC 2)

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1. Introduction

The Arctic region is warming at more than twice the rate of the global average, a phenomenon referred to as Arctic amplification – AA (Serreze and Barry 2011). Arctic ecosystems and inhabitants are heavily impacted by increased seasonal mean temperature, decreased sea ice thickness and extent, and permafrost destabilization (AMAP 2017). The triggers and feedback mechanisms of AA are not clearcut yet, and current climate models do not cover the complex local processes at play, particularly aerosol–climate interactions (Schmale et al. 2021). A key to understand the contribution of aerosols to AA is to characterize regional and seasonal processes including aerosol sources, transformation and resulting climate effects.

One of the most distinctive features of aerosol patterns in the High Arctic, including Svalbard, is a typical annual cycle with a maximum aerosol mass in late winter and early spring, commonly referred to as Arctic haze (Quinn et al. 2007). Haze chemical composition has been monitored on the seasonal

scale at several sites in the Arctic since the early 1980s. No change in sulphate concentrations was observed during the 1980s, but in the 1990s they began to decline due to the decrease in S emissions from Eurasia, western Europe and North America (AMAP 2006). In the 2000s and 2010s, sulphate decline along the year is instead barely detectable (Sharma et al. 2019).

Nevertheless, monthly analysis showed that sulphate decrease from year to year mostly occurs during haze months and this was reasonably ascribed to anthropic sulphate. Here we confirm that this assumption is correct, by applying the same monthly analysis exclusively to the anthropic fraction of sulphate, as assessed by a chemical source apportionment method (Amore et al. 2022), also including more recent data (now covering the 2010–2022 time period). We also show that anthropic sulphate levels remain relatively constant in summer, suggesting that it is hitting its background level.

2. The state of Arctic haze in Svalbard

Arctic aerosol is generally characterized by a strong seasonality, resulting in different processes and sources dominating at different times of the year: anthropic pollution from long-range transport in winter/spring and natural emissions from regional sources in summer/autumn. Aerosol in Svalbard follows such a cycle, with a maximum in mass and species concentration in spring, due to Arctic haze, and a maximum in aerosol particle number in summer due to increased new particle formation processes (AMAP 2006).

As also reported in the original HAZECLIC chapter (Traversi et al. 2021), sulphate is the main component of the haze, and is usually taken as the chemical marker of this phenomenon. In that chapter, sulphate trends were studied at two sites in Ny-Ålesund (Gruvebadet – GVB and Zeppelin -

ZEP) allowing the detection of a decreasing trend along the 2010–2020 period, mostly related to a decrease during the haze months, whereas a slight increase during summer was observed. As reported in topical papers (Sharma et al. 2019), a similar decrease was observed at several Arctic sites and was caused by the decline in S emission from the former Soviet Union, North America and western Europe during the 1990s.

Despite being mainly anthropic in origin, sulphate in the haze arises also from natural sources. The anthropic fraction was estimated both for GVB and ZEP sites via a simple chemical source apportionment method, as described in Amore et al. (2022). Four different source contributions to sulphate were quantified for each sample, namely sea salt, crustal, biogenic and anthropogenic. It has

to be noticed that biogenic contribution at ZEP is affected by a larger uncertainty than at GVB since methanesulphonic (MSA) concentration, which was the indicator used to assess this fraction, is not available from ZEP. We chose to use MSA concentrations from GVB as best possible approximation. Interestingly, sulphate from crustal sources is present all through the year. This can be ascribed to resuspension of dust both from local sources (when the surrounding areas are ice-free, from late spring to early autumn) and to long-range sources, including Arctic haze (Quinn et al. 2002). The dust source areas in the Arctic were studied in detail by using different back trajectory models (including HYSPLIT and LAGRANTO) by Stohl (2006). In particular, Tobo et al. (2019) observed that air masses that spent a relatively long time over Svalbard in summer 2016 were enriched in larger dust particles, hinting to a significant contribution of local sources. Also, Crocchianti et al. (2021) reported a contribution of local and long-distance dust in spring and summer 2015.

Figure 1 shows the data distribution as box plots covering the 2010–2022 time period for both GVB and ZEP. The two sites show comparable levels in general for all the apportioned components, with mean and median values in the same order of magnitude. A particularly good agreement at the sites can be observed for the anthropic fraction, showing mean values at GVB only 2% higher than ZEP and similar median levels as well (around 11% difference). A larger gap is shown

for biogenic fraction, which exhibits the lowest concentrations, thus carrying larger uncertainties, besides being biased by the lack of MSA data at ZEP. The comparability of the two data sets shows the robustness of the sampling, measurement, and data elaboration methods at the two observatories, which so far have been deploying different strategies in terms of sampling protocols and analytical methods.

Figure 2 shows anthropic sulphate levels along the time period covered by both records (2010–2022). We can observe that both absolute concentration levels and the seasonal pattern of this fraction agree well at GVB and ZEP. We present here the raw data obtained by applying the source apportionment method to each measured sample and, despite the different temporal resolution (in some years) and different sample collection and analysis methods, the records appear to be comparable. Neither the GVB nor the ZEP series shows an obvious decline in anthropic sulphate over the years, confirming that this species is reaching its lower limit, although the overall picture appears different in close-up (see monthly analysis in Figure 3). The possible correspondence of short-term events at GVB and ZEP is worthy of interest, especially as it may enable definition of structure of the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) but accurate data elaboration (resampling and outlier treatment) would be required to compare the records on the short scale with statistical significance.

Figure 1: Data distribution plots of the different sulphate contributions (sea salt, crustal, biogenic, anthropic) at GVB and ZEP observatories in the 2010–2022 time period.

Figure 2: Temporal profile of anthropic sulphate at GVB (dark blue) and ZEP (light blue) observatories as reconstructed by chemical atmospheric series in the 2010–2022 time period.

Figure 3: March and September monthly averages of anthropic sulphate in every year between 2010 and 2022 at GVB (black and brown) and ZEP (grey and yellow) observatories. Vertical bars represent monthly standard deviation.

The good agreement of anthropic sulphate series (as well as the other fractions) at GVB and ZEP can also be seen in the monthly averages of the four sources' contributions to sulphate in spring and summer periods (Figure 4). Since year-round measurements were started at GVB only in 2018, we chose to consider only the time from March to September, which is covered by observations at both sites throughout the 2010–2022 period. The pattern of the haze is quite evident in Figure 4, with anthropic sulphate reaching 630 (GVB) and 570 (ZEP) ng m^{-3} in April, decreasing significantly in

May (by 36% and 23%, respectively) and reaching the lowest summer levels in August (95 ng m^{-3} at GVB and 125 ng m^{-3} at ZEP), 5–7 times lower than peak values. The proportion of natural sulphate is markedly lower during the haze months (13% and 15% of total sulphate at ZEP and GVB in March and April) and closer to that of anthropic sulphate in September (33% and 42% at ZEP and GVB). This feature deserves some attention because of the mentioned importance of the natural baseline and its climate change-driven variability.

Figure 4: Stack column plot displaying the monthly averages of sulphate contributions (sea salt – blue; crustal – red; biogenic – black; anthropic – grey) at GVB and ZEP for the entire period 2010–2022.

Anthropic sulphate shows no clear trend through the 2010–2022 period, neither at GVB nor at ZEP, where the dataset is larger and more complete (Figure 2). The detection of recent trends is complicated by the effect of natural variations on seasonal and annual time scales. Hence, to remove seasonal variability from the trend analyses, we compared average monthly concentrations, similarly to Traversi et al. (2021). We selected March and September as representative of two different scenarios: haze-on and haze-off, respectively. Unlike the previous SESS Report we can observe here (Figure 3) the behaviour of the exclusively anthropogenic sulphate at different times of the year. Anthropogenic sulphate in March features a net decrease at both sites, with a similar slope along the investigated 13 years, reaching concentrations in 2022 which are about two thirds to half of those measured in 2010 at both sites. GVB shows a larger inter-annual variability than ZEP and its linear correlation is worse ($R^2 = 0.263$ at GVB, $R^2 = 0.618$ at ZEP). This difference in variability may possibly be caused by GVB being more sensitive than ZEP to local production sources and short-

range transport (Graßl et al. 2022). Nevertheless, anthropic sulphate series at both sites hint that sulphate concentrations were still actively declining also in the last decade. Conversely, no clear trend can be detected in the September averages over the 2010–2022 time period. Both sites exhibit essentially constant levels of anthropic sulphate in this month, all through the years. Previous results (Traversi et al. 2021) showed a slight increase total sulphate concentrations in September at both sites. Now that we have added two years of data, identified the anthropic fraction (which actually accounts for the largest part of sulphate, even in September) and based our calculations solely on that fraction, anthropic sulphate does not show a significant increase in September over the last decade.

According to these results, it appears that the anthropic contribution during haze-off times (as in September) has reached its lower limit, a sort of “background level” that does not decrease further as years go on. Conversely, during haze-on times (as in March), the anthropic contribution is

still decreasing, possibly due to stricter air quality policies, globally leading to fewer aerosols and precursors being transported to the Arctic. Such an effect is promising, in principle, especially

considering that more intense socioeconomic activities in the Arctic will probably lead to enhanced local emissions, directly affecting cloud coverage and local albedo.

3. Contributions to interdisciplinarity

The data yielded by the simultaneous observation of two sites (GVB and ZEP) both located in Ny-Ålesund at different altitudes and differently related to the ABL, can be useful for a number of modelling studies (vertical structure of the ABL, anthropic and natural aerosol sources, atmospheric circulation processes on different geographical scale, Ice Nucleating Particle production).

Interaction with the glaciological community working in Arctic sites would be welcome to constrain the aerosol deposition processes (besides production and transport), hence its impact on the cryosphere. This connection could also work the other way round, with current aerosol observations serving as calibration tools for past chemical records archived in firn and ice cores.

Major improvements to the Earth observing system in Svalbard since the publication of our previous chapter (Traversi et al. 2021):

- Two additional years (2021 and 2022) added to the data sets enlarging the currently available chemical series from Svalbard to 13 years; this update will allow better characterization of long-term trends and short-term events and the spatial and temporal variability of aerosol sources.

- Refinement of the sulphate proxy by apportioning different anthropic and natural contributions by means of a simple chemical source apportionment method.

4. Unanswered questions

Although the Arctic haze has received much attention in the past (AMAP 2006, 2015), key questions are still unsolved. The ongoing long-term observations at Ny-Ålesund can provide pivotal information on the following pending questions (see also section 5):

1. Discrimination of the two modes of the Arctic haze: the so-called “chronic Arctic haze” (the low variance climatological annual cycle) and the episodic events of long-range transported pollutants.
2. Address numerous modelling issues for Arctic processes. Continuous observations at high resolution can help in constraining current models. The available model estimates of anthropogenic

aerosol are affected by various uncertainties such as lack of feedback from variability in natural aerosol input, treatment of aerosol mixing state and hygroscopicity, contribution of precursor gases to secondary organic aerosol formation (Schmale et al. 2021), interaction between sea salt aerosol (which can significantly contribute to wintertime Arctic aerosol budget) and other inorganic aerosol components which have a dominant anthropic (haze) origin such as sulphate and nitrate.

3. More detailed characterization of the vertical structure of the ABL in the Kongsfjorden area, not only during spot campaigns but all through the year, since the GVB observatory can be considered representative of ground-level aerosol concentrations and is well within the ABL whereas

ZEP observatory has a more complex relationship with the ABL (often above the ABL during winter season and only sometimes within it in summer) (Graßl et al. 2022).

4. Better definition of the “moving natural aerosol baseline” (Schmale et al. 2021). This novel research focus is related to the knowledge of the anthropic aerosol emissions (including the Arctic haze) since the “natural” processes are affected by the environmental changes induced, in their turn, by the anthropic activity. The “moving baseline” concept reflects the continuous changes that natural aerosol emission and production processes undergo upon being perturbed by the ongoing climate change (Schmale et al. 2021). Such interplay

between anthropic forcing and natural processes can be better understood by apportioning aerosol natural sources by means of specific markers and experimental and modelling efforts. In this context, particular attention should be paid to marine biogenic trace gases (DMS) and related aerosol oxidation products (MSA and sulphate) (see also Recommendations 2 and 3). In fact, Svalbard is becoming a warmer environment, and retreating sea ice there could increase the number of NPF events in the future, since most precursor gases originate from biogenic sources within the nearby ocean. The growth of these particles can lead to reflective low-level clouds over the “dark” sea surface.

5. Recommendations for the future

The data and results presented in this update chapter allow us to reiterate two previous recommendations and propose a new one.

1. The continuous long-term measurements at two strategic sites (GVB and ZEP) should be maintained. Given that these two observatories are both located in Ny-Ålesund but at different elevations, the simultaneous observation of key aerosol chemical markers can help discriminating the impact of the haze both at ground level and above the ABL, thus gaining a local and long-range signature of this phenomenon. In this view, it is recommended to harmonize the protocols for aerosol sampling and measurements between the two sites. A preliminary effort in this direction is being accomplished within the Italian PRA “BETHA-NyÅ” project (2021–2024).

2. The natural Arctic “baseline” should be unraveled (see also section 4.). As outlined in the previous section, an accurate evaluation of the “moving natural aerosol baseline” is needed to better understand how anthropic activities impact the environment. This requires a more detailed knowledge about natural Arctic aerosol emissions, their evolution and transport, as well as of their effects on cloud microphysics. To this aim, the

measurement of MSA also at ZEP observatory would provide an asset to quantify the biogenic contribution to sulphate budget in at Ny-Ålesund area. In fact, MSA is a univocal marker of marine biological activity, also in relation to sea ice dynamics (Becagli et al. 2019) and sulphate/MSA ratio has been used here just to assess the contribution of this source at GVB site.

Based on the results here presented and on the latest developments of the research in the Arctic the following new recommendation is proposed:

3. Upgrade the GVB observation facility with the measurement of trace gases using on-line instruments. Expanding the current observation set at Gruvebadet (mainly devoted to the aerosol phase) with year-round continuous measurements of key gaseous species would provide an extended overview of the gas–aerosol–cloud interaction, which is crucial for a better understanding of climate change in the Arctic. One of the main effects of climate change is the loss of Arctic Sea ice, which was found to cause an increase in the phytoplankton net primary production in the last two decades. This is likely to lead to an increase in the emissions of primary biogenic precursors such

as DMS, which undergo chemical transformation in the atmosphere. The oxidation products of DMS (MSA and H₂SO₄), together with NH₃ and amines, act as aerosol precursors contributing to NPF processes and thus influencing cloud formation and radiative balance (Xavier et al. 2022).

The recommended enlargement of GVB facility might be implemented via off-line or on-line instruments, depending on what is economically

feasible. On-line instrumentation would certainly imply a higher cost in the start-up phase but would be more convenient in terms of human resources and consumables, besides having the potential to yield a continuous high-resolution record. A preliminary successful effort has already been accomplished at GVB and ZEP within the Ny-Ålesund Aerosol Cloud Experiment (NASCENT) (Pasquier et al. 2022).

6. Data availability

Dataset	Parameter	Period	Location	Metadata access (URL)	Dataset provider
PM10 chemistry at GVB*	Apportioned sulphate concentration in PM10 (anthropic, sea salt, crustal, biogenic)	2010–2022	GVB, Ny-Ålesund	Italian Arctic Data https://metadata.iadc.cnr.it/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/a72d871b-01f0-4b20-993d-d6855eefb0d6	Rita Traversi rita.traversi@unifi.it Mirko Severi Mirko.severi@unifi.it Silvia Becagli Silvia.becagli@unifi.it
PM10 chemistry at ZEP**	Anthropic sulphate concentration in PM10	2010–2022	ZEP, Ny-Ålesund	https://ebas-data.nilu.no/Pages/DataSetList.aspx?key=650ADEFD22EB414580B96BB622396E85	EBAS NILU

* GVB: Gruvebadet

** ZEP: Zeppelin Observatory

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Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System – Knowledge Centre, operational phase 2022.

8. References

AMAP (2006) Arctic Pollution 2006. Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP), Oslo, Norway. vii+28 pp.

AMAP (2015) AMAP Assessment 2015: Black carbon and ozone as Arctic climate forcers. Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP), Oslo, Norway. vii + 116 pp.

AMAP (2017) Adaptation Actions for a Changing Arctic: Perspectives from the Bering-Chukchi-Beaufort Region. Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP), Oslo, Norway. xiv + 255pp

Amore A, Giardi F, Becagli S, Caiazzo L, Mazzola M, Severi M, Traversi R (2022) Source apportionment of sulphate in the High Arctic by a 10 yr-long record from Gruvebadet Observatory (Ny-Ålesund, Svalbard Islands). *Atmospheric Environment* 270:118890. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2021.118890>

Becagli S, Amore A, Caiazzo L, Di Iorio T, di Sarra A, Lazzara L, Marchese C, Meloni D, Mori G, Muscari G, Nuccio C, Pace G, Severi M, Traversi R (2019) Biogenic aerosol in the Arctic from eight years of MSA data from Ny Ålesund (Svalbard Islands) and Thule (Greenland). *Atmosphere* 10:349. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos10070349>

Crocchianti S, Moroni B, Waldhauserová PD, Becagli S, Severi M, Traversi R, Cappelletti D (2021) Potential Source Contribution Function Analysis of High Latitude Dust Sources over the Arctic: Preliminary Results and Prospects. *Atmosphere* 12:347. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos12030347>

Graßl, S, Ritter C, Schulz A (2022) The Nature of the Ny-Ålesund Wind Field Analysed by High-Resolution Windlidar Data. *Remote Sens* 14:3771. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14153771>

Pasquier JT, David RO, Freitas G, Gierens R, Gramlich Y, Haslett S, et al (2022) The Ny-Ålesund Aerosol Cloud Experiment (NASCENT) Overview and First Results. *BAMS* 103:11, E2533-E2558. <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-21-0034.1>

Quinn P, Miller T, Bates T, Ogren J, Andrews E, Shaw G (2002) A 3-year record of simultaneously measured aerosol chemical and optical properties at Barrow, Alaska. *J Geophys Res* 107(D11): NO. D11, 10.1029/2001JD001248. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2001JD001248>.

Quinn PK, Shaw G, Andrews E, Dutton EG, Ruoho-Airola T, Gong SL (2007) Arctic haze: current trends and knowledge gaps. *Tellus* 59B:99–114. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0889.2006.00236.x>

Schmale J, Zieger P, Ekman AML (2021) Aerosols in current and future Arctic climate. *Nat. Clim. Chang.* 11:95–105. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-020-00969-5>

Serreze MC, Barry RG (2011) Processes and impacts of Arctic amplification: A research synthesis. *Global Planet. Change* 77(1):85–96. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloplacha.2011.03.004>

Sharma S, Barrie LA, Magnusson E, Brattstrom G, Leaitch WR, Steffen A, Landsberger S (2019) A factor and trends analysis of multidecadal lower tropospheric observations of arctic aerosol composition, black carbon, ozone, and mercury at Alert, Canada. *J Geophys Res Atmos* 124(24):14133–14161. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019JD030844>

Stohl A (2006) Characteristics of atmospheric transport into the Arctic troposphere. *J Geophys Res* 111:D 11306. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2005JD006888>

Tobo Y, Adachi K, DeMott PJ, Hill TCJ, Hamilton DS, Mahowald NM, Nagatsuka N, Ohata S, Uetake J, Kondo Y, Koike M (2019) Glacially sourced dust as a potentially significant source of ice nucleating particles. *Nat Geosci* 12:253–258. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-019-0314-x>

Traversi R, Becagli S, Severi M, Caiazzo L, Mazzola M, Lupi A, Fiebig M, Hermansen O, Krejci R (2021) Arctic Haze in a climate changing world: the 2010-2020 trend. In: Moreno-Ibáñez et al (eds) SESS report 2020, Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System, Longyearbyen, pp 104-117. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4293826>

Xavier C, Baykara M, Wollesen de Jonge R, Altstädter B, Clusius P, Vakkari V et al (2022) Secondary aerosol formation in marine Arctic environments: a model measurement comparison at Ny-Ålesund. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* 22:10023–10043. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-22-10023-2022>

Polar Night in Ny-Ålesund. (Photo: Simonetta Montaguti, CNR-ISP)